

Effects of Reward on Performance of Workers in the Nigerian Public Sector

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ABSTRACT

Service delivery in Nigeria's public sector has assumed greater significance given that much is required of the civil service if government is to successfully execute its policies and programmes. However, for effective and efficient service delivery and improved job performance in the public sector, workers need to be appropriately motivated. It is in view of the foregoing that this study was designed to examine the effect of reward on employee's performance in Oyo State civil service. The study was anchored on motivational theory of equity which sees performance as consequence of fair treatment of employees. To address the study problems, descriptive survey design was adopted. The population of the study comprises of 7,785 employees of the Ministries, Departments and Agencies (MDAs) of the Oyo State Civil Service. A sample size 381 was drawn by the use of Talo Yamanes formula of which 200 copies of questionnaires was duly completed and returned and this represents 52.5% response rate. In line with the study objectives, four hypotheses were formulated and tested using simple regression analysis and t-test analysis through the use of the 22nd version of SPSS. The findings revealed significant individual and joint effect of financial and non-financial rewards on performance. In addition, the study discovered that non-financial reward in comparison to financial reward significantly impacted more on performance. In view of the findings, the study recommended that it is high time government knew what propels its workforce to improved productivity. In particular, in-service training, merit-based promotion, recognition, meritorious service awards, recommendation and other forms on non-financial reward were advocated while not forgetting performance-based-incentives.

KEYWORDS: Worker performance, Reward, service delivery, public sector, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Background of the study

Over the years, organizations have been faced with the need to increase productivity and efficiency; this has led scholars and management practitioners to be interested in the area of management of motivational rewards and performance. There has also been a growing interest in determining factors that sustain and help improve employee performance, one of which is reward. According to Milkovich and Newman (2008), management of reward systems ensures the creation and sustenance of competitive advantage for organisations. Thus, organisations that want to win in the marketplace must be ready to effectively reward its people who are its most valuable assets.

As Armstrong (2008) observed, reward, whether monetary or non-monetary, is an issue that is very important to the employees. It is a means through which management compensate employees for making themselves available at the workplace and for a job well done. Reward, which comes in form of wages and salaries, incentives, fringe benefits, profit-sharing, etc., is not only to compensate workers but also to motivate them for better performance.

In drawing the linkage between reward and performance, Adams Stacey in his equity theory proposed that when workers are of the feeling or perceived that their input (knowledge, skills, attitudes and competences) are coherent and consistent with their output (reward) both internally and externally, they will perform well on the job. An employee who feels there is a disconnect between his input and what he is being paid are prone to be de-motivated and dissatisfied which will eventually affect his performance (Maduabum, 2006).

The essence of effective reward management is the achieving of organizational goals and objectives. Employees that are compensated in the right manner are expected to give their best in terms of performance to the organisation. Now, it is pertinent to ask: do reward paid to employees affect how they perform on the job? This and many other questions are what this paper intends to answer.

Statement of the Problem

The Nigerian Public Service has been in existence since independence. Workers in the public service whether at the

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state or federal level are rewarded according to a consolidated structure designed for that purpose. This structure specifies wages and salaries to be paid to workers at different levels and steps. Having being paid, public servants are expected to be professional and display expertise at all times. However, many have argued or opined that the hallmark of the Nigerian Civil Service is inefficiency, low productivity and corruption.

In the past, several reforms have been done to improve the moral and productivity level of civil servants. A typical example is the Udoji Awards of 1974 done by General Yakubu Gowon. Other leaders including Former President Obasanjo also saw to the improvement in the pay of civil servants with the increase in minimum wage to N18,000. He also brought about monetization of civil servants' fringe benefits amidst other reforms. Despite improvement in civil servants reward, the service is still characterised with low productivity occasioned by low workers performance. On this note, the study intends to investigate the problem of low performance in the civil service and that whether reward given to the civil servants affect their performance at work.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective is to critically examine the role of reward in the performance of civil servants in Oyo State, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Determine whether there is a joint effect of wages and salaries and recognition on employee performance.
2. Assess the effect of wages and salaries on employee performance.
3. Determine the effect of recognition on employee performance.
4. Compare the effect of wages and salaries and recognition in relation to employee performance

Research Questions

To further help in creating an insight into the problem under study, the following questions have been formulated.

1. What is the combined effect of wages and salaries and recognition on employee performance?
2. To what extent does wages and salaries effect performance in the civil service under the study?
3. What extent does recognition effect employee performance?
4. To what extent do wages and salaries and recognition differ on their effect on employee performance?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses are formulated.

1. There is no significant joint effect of wages and salaries and recognition
2. There is no significant effect of wages and salaries on employee performance.
3. Recognition does not have significant effect on employee performance.
4. Recognition does not affect significantly more on employee performance than wages and salaries.

REVIEW OF RELEVANT LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Reward is construed in Bratton and Gold (2003) as *all the cash, non-cash and psychological payments provided by an organization in return for their contribution*. The definition provided by Malhotra, Budhwar and Prowse (2007)

indicates that rewards encompass all benefits workers receive from their workplace. Such rewards, Pattanayak (2005) explained can come in many forms: basic salary, compensation, insurance, profit sharing, retirement plans, employee stock, overtime pay, attendance incentives, competition and contests, output-oriented merit increases, performance bonuses, piecework, safety incentives, awards etc.

For Puwanenthiren (2011), an organisation's system of reward consists of several components namely - people, process, rules and decision making activities involved in the allocation of compensation and benefits to employees in exchange for their contribution to the organization. In all, reward is seen as appreciation in cash or in kind given to employees for their extra contributions to the organization (Thomson, 2002).

Rewards can be financial or non-financial (Mbah, Mgbemena & Ejike, 2015). According to literature as reported in Nnaji-Ihedinmah and Egbunike (2015), the traditional, quantifiable elements of reward such as salary, variable pay and benefits are known as financial rewards while intangible non-cash elements such as scope to achieve and exercise responsibility, career opportunities, learning and development, the intrinsic motivation provided by the work itself and the quality of working life provided by the organization belong to the group of non-financial reward.

Perhaps the foregoing may explain why reward is believed in Gross and Friedman (2004) to include compensation (consisting of basic pay, short and long term incentives), benefits (health issues, work/ life, and other benefits), and careers (training and development, career progression); which may be used to attract, retain, motivate and satisfy employees (Armstrong, 2013).

In the same vein, Tumwet (2013) identified non-financial reward to include, challenging tasks, opportunity for personal development, autonomy and responsibility, teamwork, job security, professionally stimulating environment, opportunity to set performance goals, predictable work life, opportunity to lead, training and development and flexible work policies. For Ekpudu and Okafor (2012) as well Ekpudu and Ojeifo (2014), financial rewards are monies spent by the organisation on the employee in order to influencing them to have favourable attention towards goals achievement in the organisation.

The concept of employee performance refers to all organisational outputs attributable to the employee (Ejiemudo, 2014). Similarly, Bale and Holton (2009) construed employee performance as a record of all outcomes traceable to the employee in an organisation. In the same vein, employee performance is seen in terms of behaviour and results attributable to the employee (Brumback, 2010). As reported in Mba, Mgbemena and Ejike (2015), employee performance is simply all behaviours of the employee towards organisational goals.

On the other hand, the concept of civil service is described as the administrative machinery through which the work of government is carried out (Ezeani, 2006). For Anyim, Ufodiama and Olusanya (2013), the public sector in which the civil service remains an integral part, consists of

government agencies, ministries and extra-ministerial departments. According to Imhonopi and Urim (2013, p.79), it is through the ministries, departments and agencies of the civil service manned by seasoned technocrats that government pursues its policies, programmes and services that help galvanize development at all levels, engender economic progress and increase trust and connection between the managers of the state and the people.

Theoretical Framework

Equity theory is a theory that attempts to explain employee performance in terms of perceptions of fair/unfair distributions of resources within the organisation. Equity theory was first developed in 1963 by John Stacey Adams. Considered one of the justice theories, the underlying assumption in the theory is that employees seek to maintain equity between what they bring to the organisation and what the organisation offers in return. (Adams, 1965). Thus the belief is that employees value fair treatment which causes them to perform or even surpass what is expected of them in the organisation. In essence, equity in the workplace is based on the ratio of performance (inputs) to rewards (outcomes).

Adams' theory states that employees struggle for equity between themselves and other employees. Equity is achieved when the ratio of employee outcomes over inputs is equal to other employee outcomes over inputs (Adams, 1965). Proponents of Adam's theory would argue for example that so long as Oyo State civil service employees' inputs (performance) are matched by their level of reward, Oyo State civil service employees would be inclined to perform more to attract better reward since their efforts determine how they would be rewarded (which is in itself, a fair process).

Theoretical Review

In further elucidation of reward among employees as it relates to their performance, it is pertinent to discuss the Equity Theory. It has long been established that perceived inequity in payment matters can be highly damaging to an organization. Classic studies undertaken by J. S. Adams (1963) found that a key determinant of satisfaction at work is the extent to which employees judge pay levels and pay increases to be distributed fairly. These led to the development by Adams and others of equity theory which holds that we are very concerned that rewards or 'outputs' equate to our 'inputs' (defined as skill, effort, experience, qualifications, etc) and that these are fair when compared with the rewards being given to others. According to Adam, employees are motivated for performance and will eventually perform only when they perceive both internal and external equity with their pay.

Internal equity refers to the pay relationship among different jobs/skills/competencies within a single organization while external competitiveness refers to the pay relationships among organizations – the organization's pay relative to its competitors (Milkovich & Newman, 2008). According to Milkovich and Newman employees tend to judge the fairness of their organization's internal pay structure by making multiple comparisons of comparing their jobs with jobs similar to their own, to others at the same employer, and their jobs' pay against external pay levels.

On internal equity, Torrington et al (2008) wrote that whatever methods are used to determine pay levels and to decide what elements make up the individual pay package, employers must ensure that they are perceived by employees to operate equitably. This internal equity can only be maintained if an effective job evaluation is carried out in order to evaluate the monetary values of each job in the organization and how they relate to each other. However, the challenge has been that job evaluation processes also possess some inherent problems that has caused arguments especially on what should constitute compensable factors for each job and what should not. Also the appropriate job evaluation method to use out of the various options available, and whether to evaluate jobs based on the job contents or the skills, competences, and attitudes of the person that would perform the job.

Where employees believe that they are not being fairly rewarded, they show signs of 'dissonance' or dissatisfaction which leads to absence, voluntary turnover, on-job shirking and low-trust employee relations. It is therefore important that an employer not only treats employees equitably in payment matters but is seen to do so too. While it is difficult to gain general agreement about who should be paid what level of salary in an organization, it is possible to employ certain clear principles when making decisions in the pay field. Those that are the most important are the following:

1. A standard approach for the determination of pay;
2. A little subjective or arbitrary decision making as is feasible;
3. Maximum communication and employee involvement in establishing pay determination mechanisms;
4. Clarity in pay determination matters so that everyone knows what the rules are and how they are applied.

Empirical Review

In terms of employee performance, there are many factors that affect employee performance like working conditions, worker and employer relationship, training and development opportunities, job security, and company's overall policies and procedures for rewarding employees, etc. Among all those factors which affect employee performance, motivation that comes with rewards is of utmost importance (Akatr *et al.*, 2012). Thus, literature has identified reward as route organizations can employ to increase employee performance (Al-Nsour 2012; Osibanjo, Abiodun & Fadugba, 2012; Falola, Ibidunni & Olokundun, 2014). In the same vein, Arnold (2013) reported that organisational rewards are designed to get the maximum performance from the employees and help retain the most productive among labour.

Over the years it has been proved that one of the means through which an organisation can use to improve on workers performance and productivity is fair remuneration and reward (Pratheepkanth, 2011). With the current economic trend and dynamism in the business environment, organisations which must compete favourably with others must be ready to do everything possible to improve their employees' performances. To buttress this, Vroom (1964) had opined that employees often perform more on the job if there pay is tied to performance which has been objectively evaluated.

Researchers such as Pratheepkanth (2011), Obasan (2012), Harunavamwe & Kanengoni (2013) and many others have carried out studies to investigate the impact reward employees receive have on their performance. The researchers have argued that reward leads to motivation and satisfaction which in turn results to improved performance. Akerele (1991) in his study found that returns made by organisations always determines how much will be paid as reward to employees. He stated further that such difference in wages between high and low reward earners contribute to low morale, low performance and low productivity.

Nwachukwu (1994) in his study also found that the low productivity among employees in Nigeria can be traced to many factors and prominent among them is inadequate reward given to employees by employers of labour. The study further submitted that the manner in which the privileged few in the society who have not really worked hard display their ill-gotten wealth also serves as a demoralizing factor for employees who are working hard to get peanuts.

Pratheepkanth (2011) in studying the relationship between reward and employee motivation investigated commercial bank workers in Srilanka and found that a significant relationship exist between reward and employee motivation. The study was also able to conclude that the higher the employee reward, the higher the motivation they have to perform better on the job and vice versa.

Similarly, Harunavamwe and Kanengoni (2013) investigated the impact of monetary and non-monetary rewards on motivation. Unlike Pratheepkanth, they found a moderate significant relationship between non-monetary reward and employee motivation, and no significant relationship between monetary reward and motivation of workers.

On empirical studies among public servants, Okwudili (2015) also carried out a study on the effect of non-monetary reward on productivity of employees among selected government parastatals in Abia State. The study concluded that higher productivity and efficiency of employees in government parastatals are possible with the effective exploitation of human resource through non-monetary rewards implementation.

Ejumudo (2004) also investigated the relationship between reward system management and staff performance in Delta State Civil Service. Ejumudo (2004)'s study found that the incongruence of the pay reward system of the Delta State civil service and the central guiding principle of fairness, cost of living and moderation, the in-grained culture of poor performance and dysfunctional employee mode of entry have negatively impacted on the performance of the staff. The implication of the finding is that poor performance and low productivity being experienced from the civil servants is a result of poor and lack of adequate pay reward to them.

Bello and Adebajo (2014) also studied reward system and employee performance among public secondary school teachers in Lagos State, Nigeria. They found a significant direct relationship between the performance of the teachers and their salary package. Also they found that allowances and access to training of the teachers also affect their

performance on the job. They concluded that workers reward package matters a lot and that employers should take it seriously as most of the employees express displeasure with their reward through poor performance and non-commitment to their job.

Ghazanfar *et al.* (2011) argued that previous literature revealed that to achieve organizational goals and objectives, the human resource of the organization must be adequately rewarded for them to be well motivated and engaged. In their study of the relationship between work motivation and satisfaction, they found that satisfaction with compensation can be factor of work motivation and that flexible pay is not a motivating factor in the jobs which the employees were holding. Ghazanfar *et al.* (2011) further found that benefits do not have a significant impact on work motivation. Hence, from their study they concluded that intrinsic reward tends to motivate workers more than extrinsic rewards.

Finally, researchers have attempted to compare financial and non-financial reward in relation to employee performance. For instance, Grant and Singh (2011) argued that traditional financial reward schemes such as stock option and bonuses are often beneficial for motivating and improving employee performance, but with some negative consequences such as unethical behaviour, heighten employee turnover rate, envy and fuel discontent among employee when not well applied in an organization.

As explained in Azoulay, Graff-Zivin and Manso, (2010), it is the long term rewards rather than short term rewards which non-financial reward offer that help to motivate employees in their work and promote overall greater creativity. According to Tumwet (2013) among the non-financial incentives with significant influence on performance were: opportunity for personal development, autonomy and responsibility, teamwork, job security, professionally stimulating environment, opportunity to set performance goals, predictable work life, opportunity to lead, training and development and flexible policies.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

According to Nachmias and Nachmais (1985), a research design is an integral part of the research methodology which serves as a blue print that addresses the problem of scientific inquiry. In the same vein, a research design could be described as a map or plan of action showing step-by-step procedure for accomplishing the research task. For the present study, the survey method is employed because it makes possible the formation and testing of hypotheses.

Area of the Study

The research setting is the civil service of Oyo State, Nigeria. Oyo is one of States in Southwestern Nigeria. The civil service of Oyo State is run under various ministries, departments and agencies all of which are under the control of the government and people of Oyo State, Southwest, Nigeria.

Sources of Data

The data used were obtained from two sources namely: Primary and Secondary sources.

A. Primary Sources of Data

Primary data were generated from Oyo State Civil Services using a structured questionnaire.

B. Secondary Sources Data

Secondary data were collected from published sources (annual reports, handbooks and pamphlets) of Oyo State Civil Services Commission. So also are the information from the internet, Newspapers, books, journals/magazines, Government Geffecazettes, amongst others.

Population of the Study

The population of this study, which by definition is the totality of observations with which we are concerned, irrespective of its being finite or infinite (Walpole, 1974) includes all the 7,785 top, middle and lower level staff presently active in the employment of the Oyo State government.

The breakdown is as follows:

Table3.1 Population of Oyo State Civil Service

DEPARTMENTS	NUMBER OF EMPLOYEES
Accountant General	124
Office of The Surveyor General	73
Auditor General For Local Government	111
Auditor General For State Government	136
Government Press	23
Governor's Office	819
Head of Service	41
House of Assembly	117
Sub Total	1444 (71)
MINISTRIES	
Ministry For Youth And Sport	42
Ministry Of Agriculture	701
Ministry Of Culture And Tourism	35
Ministry Of Economic Planning And Budget	85
Ministry Of Education	583
Ministry Of Environment	228
Ministry Of Establishment	127
Ministry Of Finance	94
Ministry Of Health	273
Ministry Of Industry	66
Ministry Of Information	72
Ministry Of Justice	131
Ministry Of Lands	109
Ministry Of Local Government	55
Ministry Of Special Duties	15
Ministry Of Trade Investment And Cooperative	179
Ministry Of Water Resources	14
Ministry Of Women Affairs	179
Ministry Of Works	565
Sub Total	3553 (174)
AGENCIES	
Agency For Youth Development	63
Agricultural Credit Corporation	48
Board Of Internal Revenue	688
OYSADEP	406
Pension Board	36
Sport Council	148
SUBEB Headquarters	107
TESCOM Headquarters	39
Urban and Regional Planning	446
Water Cooperation Of Oyo State	521
BOTAVED	87
Civil Service Commission	43
Council For Arts And Culture	66
House Of Assembly Service Commission	17
Judiciary Service Commission	13
Library Board	60
Sub Total	2788
GRAND TOTAL	7785 (381)

Source: Field Survey, 2016

Sample Size

Given that the population of the study is finite, a sampling procedure was carefully chosen. Denga & Ali (1983, p.61) describe sampling as the procedure of selecting or drawing from some population of possible causes with the aim of ensuring that the portion of the population being selected is representative of the population. In calculating the sample size therefore, the statistical formula for selecting from a finite population as formulated by Yamane (1964) is applied. The formula is given as:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where n = Sample size
 N = Population
 e = level of significance (or limit of tolerable error), in this case, 0.05
 I= Constant value

But N = 7,785
 $\therefore n = \frac{7,785}{1+7,785(0.05)^2}$
 = **381** This gives a sample size of 381.

Having determined the sample size, the next task was to ensure that the sample was representative enough. To this end, the study adopted Bowley (1926) proportional allocation formula to distribute the sample into different strata for the basis of data collection. The Bowley (1926) proportional allocation formula is noted for the accommodation of the different strata of the population in a sample. The Bowley (1926) proportional allocation formula is given as:

$$n_h = \frac{nN_h}{N}$$

Where n_h = number of units allocated to each stratum.
 n=total sample size
 N_h =number of items in each stratum in the population
 N=total population

Proportion for Ministries
 $n_h = \frac{3553 \times 381}{7,785} = 174$

Proportion for Departments
 $n_h = \frac{1444 \times 381}{7,785} = 71$

Proportion for Agencies
 $n_h = \frac{2788 \times 381}{7,785} = 136$

The breakdown of a sample size and the number of questionnaires allocated to each of the sub-sets of Oyo State Civil Service is shown table in Table 3.2 below.

Table3.2: Breakdown of Sample drawn from Oyo State Civil Service in Various Units

Organizations	Population	Sample
Ministries	3553	174
Departments	1444	71
Agencies	2788	136
Total	7785	381

Source: Field Survey, 2016

Table3.3: Research population, sample and valid responses

MINISTRY/DEPARTMENT/AGENCY	POPULATION	SAMPLE	VALID RESPONSES
ACCOUNTANT GENERAL	124	6	3
OFFICE OF THE SURVEYOR GENERAL	73	4	3
AUDITOR GENERAL FOR LOCAL GOVERNMENT	111	5	2
AUDITOR GENERAL FOR STATE GOVERNMENT	136	7	3
GOVERNMENT PRESS	23	1	1
GOVERNOR'S OFFICE	819	40	13
HEAD OF SERVICE	41	2	1
HOUSE OF ASSEMBLY	117	6	3
	1444	71	29

The items for the questionnaire were selected on the basis of review of literature as well as inputs from some civil servants known to the researcher and university lecturers not below the rank of a Senior Lecturer in the field of Management Sciences. The instrument is as contained in Appendix. The mode of distribution was through personal delivery which ensures satisfactory and high return rate of questionnaires by respondents. The researcher and his research assistants distributed three hundred and eighty one (381) copies of the questionnaire to respondents in the selected agencies, ministries and department which make up Oyo State civil service.

Instrument Validity

Instrument validity refers to the methods of determining the extent the instrument measures what it purports to measure. To validate the instrument, the questionnaire was vetted by the supervisor of the study with corrections together with his recommendations effect. To further validate the instrument, the questionnaire was applied on a pilot study basis to 30 management staff in selected public sector organizations in Oyo State (none of those who participated in Pilot study was part of the main study). According to reported in Nunnally (1978), the use of expert technique is an acceptable method of arriving at content validity. Based on the of these comments, responses and preliminary analysis of data, changes in the content, form, sequence of questions, spacing, arrangement and appearance of materials and the procedures for using the questionnaire was made in the light of corrections of the supervisor of the study before the questionnaire was finalized.

Instrument Reliability

Reliability is the test of the degree of consistency of responses collected by the use of the instrument. Copies of the research instrument were distributed to 30 respondents in selected public sector organizations in Oyo State and after two weeks, new copies of the same instruments were redistributed to the same respondents.

Li (2012) admonishes that it is necessary to conduct reliability tests to ensure that adapted scales are reliable enough. The scores from the two exercises were correlated using Pearson-product moment correlation coefficient as a statistical tool. The coefficient of reliability was found to be high, $r = 91\%$ showing that there is consistency in the items of survey. As literature explained in Pallant (2001) when Cronbach alpha coefficient value is above 0.7, the scale is reliable with the sample and or has a reliable internal consistency.

Method of Data Analysis

Following the completion of the data collection, the questionnaires were coded and analysed using Statistical Product and Services Solution (Ho, 2006. p.11) formerly known as Statistical Packages for the Social Sciences- SPSS currently in its 22nd version (Chidi, 2014, p.14). The analysis involved descriptive and inferential statistics. While descriptive analysis was deployed for demographic data, the research questions and hypotheses were analysed through moderated regression analysis (hypothesis I), Simple regression (hypothesis II & III) and t-test analysis. According to literature in Odetunde (2011) the choice of data analysis is informed by the nature and type of hypotheses formulated in the study. The outcome of the analysis is presented below.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF RESEARCH FINDINGS

Introduction

This segment focuses on the presentation, analysis and interpretation of the data collected through the research instrument. Also, discussion of the research findings is carried out. Frequency and percentage tables are used in data presentation. In addition, gathered data are statistically analyzed based on the research hypotheses with results interpreted accordingly. It would be recalled that out of the 381 copies of the questionnaire distributed to top, middle and lower management employees working with Oyo State civil service at various ministries, departments and agencies, only 200 copies representing 53% were validly completed and returned while 181(47%) were not returned as shown in Table 4.1.1

Table4.0.1: Rate of Response to Questionnaire Administered

Arm	Questionnaire Administered	Percentage Distribution	No. Returned /responded	Percentage Valid	No. not returned / responded	Percentage Invalid
Ministries	174	100%	93	24%	81	21%
Departments	71	100%	29	8%	42	11%
Agencies	136	100%	78	21%	58	15%
Total	381	100%	200	53%	181	47%

Source: Field Survey, 2016

Socio-demographic Characteristics of Respondents

In carrying out the research, a total of 381 questionnaires were distributed among the members of Oyo State Civil Service out of which 200 questionnaires were validly completed and returned for analysis and interpretation. Out of these (as could be seen in table 4.1.2), 16.0% are males while 84.0% are females; this shows that both genders were represented in the study. Age of respondents in the study varied from 20 years and above with age bracket of 30-39 years being the modal age.

Respondents were asked to provide their educational background, among which 55.0% were in the National Diploma category, 22.0% identified with Higher National Diploma Certificate, 14% were first degree holders while 9.0% hold Masters degree. This shows that the respondents are well educated to know the relevance and implication of the study.

In relation to the arm of the civil service in which the respondents were employed, 46.5% were engaged in the State Ministries, 14.5% in civil service departments while 39.0% work in State government agencies. This shows that Ministries in the State produced the highest number of participants in the study. On the employment status of the respondents, 86.0% of the respondents were Junior Staff while 14.0% were Senior/Management staff, thereby implying that majority of the participants were of junior staff category.

With regard to years of experience, 11% of the respondents have worked with Oyo State civil service for between 1-5years, 26.5% for between 6-10years, 34.0 for between 11-15 years, 20.5% for 16-20years while 13.2% for between 21years and above. Thus it can be inferred that majority of the respondents have been with Oyo State civil service for an upward of 11 years.

Table 4.1.1: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Gender		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Male	32	16.0
	Female	168	84.0
	Total	200	100.0
Age at last birthday		Frequency	Percent
Valid	20-29 years	51	25.5
	30-39 years	68	34.0
	40-49 years	46	23.0
	50-59 years	35	17.5
	Total	200	100.0
Highest educational qualification		Frequency	Percent
Valid	ND	110	55.0
	HND	44	22.0
	Bachelors' Degree	28	14.0
	Master's Degree	18	9.0
	Total	200	100.0
Arm of Civil Service Employed		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Ministries	93	46.5
	Departments	29	14.5
	Agencies	78	39.0
	Total	200	100.0
Category of employment		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Junior Staff	172	86.0
	Senior Staff	28	14.0
	Total	200	100.0
Working Experience		Frequency	Percent
Valid	1-5 years	22	11.0
	6-10 years	53	26.5
	11-15 years	68	34.0
	16-20 years	41	20.5
	21 years and above	16	13.2
	Total	200	100.0

The Respondents' view in Relation to Financial Rewards in Oyo State Civil Service

Table 4.2.1 revealed that 1.5% of the respondents disagreed to the suggestions that their wages and salaries are of industrial standards, 7.5% strongly disagreed, 7.0% were indecisive while 47.7% and 36.5% of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed respectively. Hence, these responses revealed that the wages and salaries that members of Oyo State civil service receive are of industrial standards. When asked if the organisation they work for takes care of their taxes, 21.5% of the respondents strongly agreed while 43.5% merely agreed. However, 10.5% of the respondents were indecisive, while 10.0% and 14.5% of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively. This means that the civil service takes care of employee taxes in Oyo State.

In light of the above, when asked if the workers are paid bonuses and allowances at work, 12.0% and 17.0% of the respondents expressed strong disagreement and mere disagreement respectively while 10.5% were indecisive. However, 19.0% and 41.5% of the respondents expressed strong agreement and mere agreement respectively. This particular data revealed that members of Oyo State civil service are paid bonuses and allowances at work. Moreover, when asked if commissions are included in the reward package for civil servants in Oyo State, 22.0% and 12.0% of the respondents respectively expressed mere negative and strong negative opinions respectively while 20.5% of the respondents were indecisive. However, 32.0% and 13.5% of the respondents expressed mere positive and strong positive opinion respectively to suggestions that commissions are included in the reward package for civil servants in Oyo State. This, result implies that commissions are included in the reward package for civil servants in Oyo State.

Furthermore, when asked if overtime pay forms part of the reward package for civil servants in Oyo State, 25.0% and 35.0% of the respondents were in mere support and strong support respectively, while 5.5% were indecisive. However, 16.5% and 18.0% of the respondents were in mere disagreement and strong disagreement respectively. This result shows that overtime pay forms part of the reward package for civil servants in Oyo State. In addition, when asked if pension is waiting for members of Oyo State civil service on retirement, 19.5% and 1.0% of the respondents expressed strong disagreement and mere disagreement respectively while 21.5% were indecisive. However, 17.0% and 41.0% of the respondents expressed strong agreement and mere agreement respectively. This particular data revealed that pension is waiting for members of Oyo State civil servants on retirement as part of their financial reward in service.

For the question regarding whether the financial reward package of Oyo State civil service is fair and satisfying 7.5% of the respondents disagreed to the suggestions that the financial reward package of Oyo State civil service is fair and satisfying, 21.0% strongly disagreed, 9.0% were indecisive while 39.0% and 23.5% of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed respectively. Hence, these responses revealed that the financial reward package of Oyo State civil service is fair and satisfying.

4.2.1: Observed Responses on Financial Rewards in Oyo State Civil Service

S/No	Questions	Observed Frequency/Percentage					Total
		SA	A	UD	D	SD	
Q7	My wages and salary are of industrial standards	73(36.5%)	95(47.5%)	14(7.0%)	3(1.5%)	15(7.5%)	200
Q8	The organisation I work for takes care of my taxes	43(21.5%)	87(43.5%)	21(10.5%)	20(10.0%)	29(14.5%)	200
Q9	I am paid bonuses and allowances at work	38(19.0%)	83(41.5%)	21(10.5%)	34(17.0%)	24(12.0%)	200
Q10	Commissions are included in my reward package	27(13.5%)	64(32.0%)	41(20.5%)	44(22.0%)	24(12.0%)	200
Q11	Overtime pay forms part of my reward package	50(25.0%)	70(35.0%)	11(5.5%)	33(16.5%)	36(18.0%)	200
Q12	There is a Pension waiting for me on retirement	34(17.0%)	82(41.0%)	43(21.5%)	39(19.5%)	2(1.0%)	200
Q13	The financial reward package of this organisation is fair and satisfying	47(23.5%)	78(39.0%)	18(9.0%)	42(21.0%)	15(7.5%)	200

Source: Field Survey, 2016

The Respondents' view in Relation to Non-Financial Rewards in Oyo State Civil Service

Table 4.3.1 showed that 2.0% of the respondents disagreed to the suggestions that employees of Oyo State civil service are recognized and awarded, 1.6% strongly disagreed, 1.2% were indecisive while 33.0% and 19.0% of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed respectively. Hence, these responses revealed that recognition is part of non-financial rewards for civil servants in Oyo State. When asked if awards are given to deserving employees as part of their job, 19.5% of the respondents strongly agreed while 40.0% merely agreed. However, 12.5% of the respondents were indecisive, while 11.0% and 14.0% of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively. This means that the civil service gives awards to deserving employees as part of their non-financial reward in Oyo State.

In light of the above, when asked if they have attended social functions sponsored by Oyo State civil service, 2.0% and 13.0% of the respondents expressed strong disagreement and mere disagreement respectively while 16.0% were indecisive. However, 20.0% and 49.0% of the respondents expressed strong agreement and mere agreement respectively. This particular data revealed that social functions are sponsored by Oyo State civil service as part of non-financial reward to its employees. Moreover, when asked if civil servants in Oyo State are promoted when due, 7.5% and 2.5% of the respondents respectively expressed mere negative and strong negative opinions respectively while 1.5% of the respondents were indecisive. However, 43.0% and 40.5% of the respondents expressed mere positive and strong positive opinion respectively to suggestions that commissions are included in the reward package for civil servants in Oyo State. This, result implies that civil servants in Oyo State are promoted when due.

Furthermore, when asked if commendations form part of the reward package for civil servants in Oyo State, 24.0% and 39.0% of the respondents were in mere support and strong support respectively, while 7.5% were indecisive. However, 15.5% and 18.0% of the respondents were in mere disagreement and strong disagreement respectively. This result shows that commendations form part of the non-financial reward package for civil servants in Oyo State. In addition, when asked if members of Oyo State civil service are allowed to go on vacation and study leave, 1.0% and 3.0% of the respondents expressed strong disagreement and mere disagreement respectively while 20.5% were indecisive. However, 20.5% and 55.0% of the respondents expressed strong agreement and mere agreement respectively. This particular data revealed that members of Oyo State civil service are allowed to go on vacation and study leave as part of their non-financial reward in service.

For the question regarding whether the non-financial reward package of Oyo State civil service is fair and satisfying 7.5% of the respondents disagreed to the suggestions that the financial reward package of Oyo State civil service is fair and satisfying, 2.0% strongly disagreed, 23.0% were indecisive while 27.0% and 40.5% of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed respectively. Hence, these responses revealed that the non-financial reward package of Oyo State civil service is not fair and satisfying.

4.3.1: Observed Responses on Non-Financial Rewards in Oyo State Civil Service

S/No	Questions	Observed Frequency/Percentage					Total
		SA	A	UD	D	SD	
Q14	Employees are recognized here	38(19.0%)	66(33.0%)	24(12.0%)	40(20.0%)	32(16.0%)	200
Q15	Awards are given to deserving employees as part of this job	39(19.5%)	86(43.0%)	25(12.5%)	22(11.0%)	28(14.0%)	200
Q16	I have attended social functions sponsored by this organisation	40(20.0%)	98(49.0%)	32(16.0%)	26(13.0%)	4(2.0%)	200
Q17	I get promoted when it is due	81(40.5%)	86(43.0%)	3(1.5%)	15(7.5%)	5(2.5%)	200
Q18	I have received commendations from this organization	48(24.0%)	78(39.0%)	7(3.5%)	31(15.5%)	36(18.0%)	200
Q19	I am allowed to go on vacation and study leave	41(20.5%)	110(55.0%)	41(20.5%)	6(3.0%)	2(1.0%)	200
Q20	The non-financial reward package of this organisation is fair and satisfying	4(2.0%)	15(7.5%)	46(23.0%)	54(27.0%)	81(40.5%)	200

Source: Field Survey, 2016

The Respondents' view in Relation to Employee Performance in Oyo State Civil Service

Table 4.4.1 revealed that 9.0% of the respondents disagreed to the suggestions that the type of reward they receive as employees of Oyo State civil service is such that they try to meet and surpass my work target, 1.5% strongly disagreed, 6.0% were indecisive while 51.5% and 32.0% of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed respectively. Hence, these responses revealed that the type of reward they receive as employees of Oyo State civil service is such that they try to meet and surpass my work target. In the same vein, when asked if attaining high level of performance is very important to them because employee efforts are recognized at Oyo State civil service, 26.0% of the respondents strongly agreed while 53.0% were mere agreement. However, 18.5% of the respondents were indecisive, while 1.5% and 1.0% of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively. This means that attaining high level of performance is very important to the workers because employee efforts are recognized at Oyo State civil service.

In light of the foregoing, when asked if they ensure that they put in extra effort in attaining high level of performance knowing that there is always a reward for them in working for Oyo State civil service, 1.0% and 3.0% of the respondents expressed strong disagreement and mere disagreement respectively while 11.5% were indecisive. However, 23.0% and 61.5% of the respondents expressed strong agreement and mere agreement respectively. This particular data showed that members of Oyo State civil service ensure that they put in extra effort in attaining high level of performance knowing that there is always a reward for them in working for Oyo State civil service.

Moreover, when asked if they try to avoid everything that will negatively affect their job as civil servants in Oyo State because of not knowing who may be noticing, 2.0% of the respondents expressed negative opinions while 20.0% of the respondents were indecisive. However, 56.5% and 21.5% of the respondents expressed mere positive and strong positive opinion respectively to suggestions that commissions are included in the reward package for civil servants in Oyo State. This, result implies that civil servants in Oyo State try to avoid everything that will negatively affect their job because of not knowing who may be noticing.

Furthermore, when asked if they don't like being lazy on their job because no effort goes unrewarded in Oyo State civil service, 49.5% and 18.0% of the respondents were in mere support and strong support respectively, while 22.0% were indecisive. However, 2.0% and 1.5% of the respondents were in mere disagreement and strong disagreement respectively. This result showed members of Oyo State civil service don't like being lazy on their job because no effort goes unrewarded. In addition, when asked if they make it a point of duty to be punctual and regular at work as workers efforts are usually recognized, 2.5% and 6.0% of the respondents expressed strong disagreement and mere disagreement respectively while 22.0% were indecisive. However, 20.5% and 49.0% of the respondents expressed strong agreement and mere agreement respectively. This particular data revealed that members of Oyo State civil servants make it a point of duty to be punctual and regular at work as workers efforts are usually recognized.

For the question regarding whether workers of Oyo State civil service are rewarded in working hard to contribute to the overall development of their organisation, 14.5% of the respondents disagreed, 6.0% strongly disagreed, similarly 6.0% were indecisive while 34.5% and 39.0% of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed respectively. Hence, these responses revealed that members of Oyo State civil service are rewarded in working hard to contribute to the overall development of their organisation. In similar vein, when asked if the reward they receive at Oyo State civil service is such that when workers identify problem in their work, they make sure they find solution to it, 28.5% of the respondents strongly agreed while 49.5% were mere agreement. However, 6.5% of the respondents were indecisive, while 14.5% and 1.0% of the respondents disagreed

and strongly disagreed respectively. This means that in Oyo State civil service, the reward workers receive is such that when they identify problem in their work, they make sure they find solution to it.

Finally, when asked if as civil servants in Oyo State, they are inclined to perform their duties with minimum supervision knowing that there is a reward in it, 3.0% of the respondents expressed negative opinions while 26.0% of the respondents were indecisive. However, 55.5% and 15.5% of the respondents expressed mere positive and strong positive opinion respectively to suggestions that commissions are included in the reward package for civil servants in Oyo State. This, result implies that civil servants in Oyo State servants are inclined to perform their duties with minimum supervision knowing that there is a reward in it.

4.4.1: Observed Responses on Employee Performance in Oyo State Civil Service

S/No	Questions	Observed Frequency/Percentage					Total
		SA	A	UD	D	SD	
Q21	The type of reward I receive here is such that I try to meet and surpass my work target	64 (32.0%)	103 (51.5%)	12 (6.0%)	18 (9.0%)	3 (1.5%)	200
Q22	Attaining high level of performance is very important to me because employee efforts are recognized here	52 (26.0%)	106 (53.0%)	37 (18.5%)	3 (1.5%)	2 (1.0%)	200
Q23	I ensure I put in extra effort in attaining high level of performance knowing that there is always a reward for me here	46 (23.0%)	123 (61.5%)	23 (11.5%)	6 (3.0%)	2 (1.0%)	200
Q24	Not knowing who may be noticing, I try to avoid everything that will negatively affect my job	43 (21.5%)	113 (56.5%)	40 (20.0%)	4 (2.0%)	0 (0.0%)	200
Q25	I don't like being lazy on their job because no effort goes unrewarded	36 (18.0%)	99 (49.5%)	58 (29.0%)	4 (2.0%)	3 (1.5%)	200
Q26	I make it a point of duty to be punctual and regular at work as my efforts are usually recognized	41 (20.5%)	98 (49.0%)	44 (21.5%)	12 (6.0%)	5 (2.5%)	200
Q27	I am rewarded in working hard to contribute to the overall development of this organisation	78 (39.0%)	69 (34.5%)	12 (6.0%)	29 (14.5%)	12 (6.0%)	200
Q28	The reward I receive here is such that when I identify problem in my work, I make sure I find solution to it	57 (28.5%)	99 (49.5%)	13 (6.5%)	29 (14.5%)	2 (1.0%)	200
Q29	I am inclined to perform my duties with minimum supervision knowing that there is a reward in it	31 (15.5%)	111 (55.5%)	52 (26.0%)	6 (3.0%)	0 (0.0%)	200

Testing of Hypotheses

Having analyzed the responses of the 200 respondents validly attended to the questions raised in the questionnaire, this section is devoted to the testing of the four hypotheses earlier formulated for the study.

Testing Hypothesis 1

H₀: There is no significant joint effect of wages and salaries and recognition on employee performance.

H₁: There is significant joint effect of wages and salaries and recognition on employee performance.

To test hypothesis 1 which stated that there is no significant joint effect of financial and non-financial reward on employee performance, a moderated regression analysis was conducted. To test for the joint effect of financial and non-financial reward on employee performance, financial reward was entered in step 1 of the regression model, non-financial reward in step 2 and the joint term of financial and non-financial reward (FRxNFR) entered in step 3.

Results of the moderated regression analysis in Table 5.1.1, show that financial reward contributed 9% of the variance in employee performance ($R^2 = .09, p < .05$) while non-financial reward produced 5% variance in employee performance ($R^2 = .05, p < .05$). The joint effect of financial reward and non-financial reward increased the variance in employee performance by 14% ($\Delta R^2 = .14, p < .05$). Thus rewards (both financial and non-financial) have significant effect on employee performance. Therefore, hypothesis 1 which stated that there is significant joint effect of financial and non-financial reward on employee performance is confirmed.

Table 4.5.1: Moderated Regression Analysis to test the Joint effects of Financial Reward and Non-Financial Reward (FR x NFR) on Employee Performance in Oyo State Civil Service

Dependent Variables	Independent Variables	F	R	R ²	Adj-R ²	ΔR ²
Employee Performance	Financial Reward (FR)	19.5*	.30*	.09*	.09	.-
Employee Performance	Non-Financial Reward (NFR)	9.7	.22*	.05*	.04	-
Employee Performance	FR x NFR	16.53*	.38*	.14*	.13	.14*

Source: Field Survey, 2016

Testing Hypothesis 2 and 3

H₀: There is no significant effect of wages and salaries on employee performance

H₁: There is significant effect of wages and salaries on employee performance

H₀: Recognition does not have significant impact on employee performance.

H₁: Recognition does have significant impact on employee performance.

To test hypotheses 2 (there is no significant effect of financial reward on employee performance) and 3 (non-financial reward does not have significant impact on employee performance), simple regression analysis was conducted. To test for hypotheses 2 and 3, employee performance was regressed on each of financial and non-financial reward.

Results of the analyses in Table 5.1.2 show that employee performance is significantly effected by both financial reward ($R^2 = .09, p < .01$) and non-financial reward ($R^2 = .05, p < .01$). Hence, hypotheses 2 and 3 are both confirmed. Thus, while there is significant effect of financial reward on employee performance, at the same time, non-financial reward does have significant impact on employee performance.

Table 4.5.2: Simple Regression Analysis to test the effect of Financial Reward and Non-Financial Reward on Employee Performance in Oyo State Civil Service

Dependent Variables	Independent Variables	F	R	R ²	Adj-R ²	ΔR ²
Employee Performance	Financial Reward (FR)	19.5*	.30*	.09*	.09	.-
Employee Performance	Non-Financial Reward (NFR)	9.7	.22*	.05*	.04	-

Source: Field Survey, 2016

* $P < .01, N = 200$

Testing Hypothesis 4

H₀: Recognition does not impact significantly more on employee performance than wages and salaries.

H₁: Recognition does impact significantly more on employee performance than wages and salaries

To test Hypothesis 4, which stated that recognition does not affect more on employee performance than wages and salaries, t-test analysis for independent group was conducted. Scores on financial reward in relation to employee performance were compared with scores on non-financial reward in relation to employee performance. Employee performance is the dependent variable while financial and non-financial rewards were the independent variables.

The result of the t-test analysis as displayed in Table 4.5.3 indicates a significant difference between financial and non-financial rewards in their effect on employee performance. Since the coefficient of employee performance is statistically significant, we can conclude that there is significant difference between financial and non-financial rewards in their effect t on employee performance.

Hence, Hypothesis 4 which states that recognition does impact significantly more on employee performance than wages and salaries is accepted. Table 4.5.3 summarizes the results of the t-test analysis on Hypothesis 4.

Table 4.5.3 T-test Showing the Difference Between Financial and Non-financial Reward on Employee Performance in Oyo State Civil Service

Dependent Variable	Independent Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t-value	Sig.
Employee Performance	Financial Reward	200	10.90	13.82	.98	11.15	p>0.05
	Non-Financial Reward	200	7.81	5.38	.38	20.52	p>0.05

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

The study focused on the effect of reward on employee performance using civil servants in Oyo State as a case study. The findings presented in the preceding segment were based on the objectives stated for the study and the results of the hypotheses tested at the end of the data collection and

analysis. The first objective examined the joint effect of wages and salaries and recognition on employee performance.

In view of the first objective, the study revealed that there is significant joint effect of wages and salaries and recognition on employee performance ($\Delta R^2 = .14, p < .05$). This nature of result has earlier been collaborated in studies such as Al-

Nsour (2012), Osibanjo, Abiodun and Fadugba (2012), Arnold (2013) as well as Falola, Ibidunni and Olokundun, (2014). Specifically, Mbah, Mgbaemena and Ejike (2015) reported that both financial and non-financial rewards are positively and significantly related to employee performance in Nigerian civil service.

The second objective of the study was to assess the role of wages and salaries on employee performance. In pursuance of this objective, it was discovered that there is significant effect of financial reward on employee performance ($R^2 = .09$, $p < .01$). This particular finding is in consonance with earlier literature. For instance, Bello and Adebajo (2014) studied reward system and employee performance among public sector employees in Lagos State, Nigeria. Bello and Adebajo (2014) found a significant direct relationship between the performance of the workers and their salary package

The third objective examined the link between recognition and employee performance. To this end, the study discovered that recognition effect significantly on employee performance ($R^2 = .05$, $p < .01$). This is in line with studies such as Harunavamwe and Kanengoni (2013). In particular, Okwudili (2015) found that that higher productivity and efficiency of employees in government parastatals are possible with the effective exploitation of human resource through non-monetary rewards implementation.

The fourth objective of the study compared wages and salaries and recognition in relation to their effect on employee performance. In view of this, the study found that the respondents considered recognition of greater significance in relation to their performance ($t = 20.52$, $p < .01$) than wages and salaries ($t = 11.52$, $p < .01$). As explained in Azoulay, Graff-Zivin and Manso, (2010), it is the long term rewards rather than short term rewards which non-financial reward offer that help to motivate employees in their work and promote overall greater creativity.

According to Tumwet (2013) among the non-financial incentives with significant influence on performance were: opportunity for personal development, autonomy and responsibility, teamwork, job security, professionally stimulating environment, opportunity to set performance goals, predictable work life, opportunity to lead, training and development and flexible policies.

Conclusion

The study examined the role of reward in the performance of civil servants in Oyo State Nigeria. In pursuance to the major objective of the study, conclusions could be drawn that the application of reward (in terms of a combination of financial and non-financial rewards) would impact on the performance of civil servants in Oyo State. Thus, it could be argued that in order to get the best results, organisation should consider a variety of ways to reward employees for their work.

Secondly, conclusions could be drawn based on the findings that civil servants in Oyo State value financial reward in the performance of their duties. In this instance, it could be posited that it is the belief that there are rewards such as wages, salaries, compensation, insurance, profit sharing, retirement plans, employee stock, overtime pay, attendance

incentives, competition and contests, output-oriented merit increases, performance bonuses, piecework, safety incentives etc. waiting in the wings that spur employees to action for the organisation.

In addition, it could also be concluded based on the findings that non-financial reward is a factor in the performance of duties among civil servants in Oyo State. This so because employees value the long lasting impression which the non-financial reward may create. Thus employees may be looking at rewards like promotion, recognition, awards and opportunity for training (which would guarantee their future growth).

Similarly, it could be concluded based on the findings that as a factor of performance, non-financial reward rated higher than financial reward among civil servants in Oyo State. In other words, to the employees, performance would better be improved if more emphasis is placed on rewards such as more enabling authority, recognition, praise, participating in decision making, promotion, holidays, better working environment, written recognition, gifts, formal dinners, informal parties, plaques, etc. in the organisation.

In all, the human resource constitutes the greatest asset an organisation can have to achieve and sustain competitive advantage over other firms. Hence, the need to attract, maintain and retain good employees is pertinent for every organisation. A good reward package therefore is one of the means through which organisations whether private or public can attract, maintain and retain best hands which can help improve the organisation through effective and efficient performance and productivity.

The objective of this study was to examine the effect of reward on the performance of civil servants in Oyo State, Nigeria. Having established an empirical basis for this causal relationship, the onus is on the government to review employees reward and fortify it with other packages in order to motivate workers towards sustained productivity and performance.

Recommendations

In view of the findings and conclusion above, the following recommendations are hereby submitted:

1. Government and its agencies should do a thorough review of the reward packages of civil servants and ensure that it meets the current trends in terms of living costs.
2. Conditions of service of the civil servants should be improved upon and made attractive so that civil servants will want to give their best always so as not to get disengaged.
3. Several other packages like life assurance, awards and recognition, opportunity for advancement, training and development opportunities, to mention a few, should be made available to civil servants adequately.
4. Members of the civil service should be trained and retrained on the need to be more productive and improve on their performance.
5. Performance-Based Pay should also be introduced to boost the morale of performing workers and encourage others to perform better.

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